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Satisfaction with the Healthcare System in OECD Countries

Between 2017 and 2022, satisfaction with the healthcare system in OECD countries decreased by an average of -2.03% for the considered countries. The OECD calculates satisfaction with the healthcare system, and the data is available for the period between 2017 and 2022.

Satisfaction with the healthcare system in OECD countries in 2022. Satisfaction with the healthcare system in 2022 varies significantly among different countries, highlighting a range of perceptions from excellence to concern. At the top of the ranking is Switzerland with an impressive 92%, followed closely by Belgium with 90% and Luxembourg with 85%. These high satisfaction levels can be attributed to well-funded healthcare systems, universal access to health services, and advanced medical technologies. The Netherlands (83%) and Austria (81%), along with Denmark and Norway, which share the same score, are also among the top, demonstrating their healthcare efficiency. Germany positions slightly lower with 79%, reflecting a robust system that might still face efficiency or access issues preventing even higher satisfaction. The Czech Republic, with 77%, and Japan, with 76%, show high satisfaction, suggesting that despite cultural and structural differences, they manage to provide healthcare that meets the population's expectations. Israel and the United States both stand at 75%, with the latter's result being somewhat surprising given the frequent criticism of the U.S. healthcare system, characterized by high costs and non-universal access. France, South Korea, and Sweden, all at 74%, reflect similar appreciation, indicating generally solid healthcare systems with room for improvement. Australia and the United Kingdom, with 71%, show slight dissatisfaction, possibly due to issues such as long waiting lists or variable quality of care. The same percentage is found in Costa Rica and Finland, which, while not among the top performers, maintain a positive perception of their healthcare systems. Lower down, Iceland, Ireland, and Slovenia, each at 68%, reflect decent satisfaction but indicate potential areas of concern. Spain, with 67%, and Estonia, with 66%, show that there is still work to be done to improve the perception of healthcare services. New Zealand, at 64%, and Portugal, at 63%, are in the mid-range, indicating moderate perception but with room for improvement. Italy, with 62%, indicates some dissatisfaction, possibly related to regional disparities in the quality of care. Latvia and Slovakia share a score of 60%, reflecting a rather critical perception of their healthcare systems. Turkey, with 58%, and Mexico, with 57%, show even lower satisfaction levels, probably due to insufficient infrastructure or inequalities in access to care. Canada, with a surprising 56%, is one of the developed countries with the lowest satisfaction, suggesting significant issues in the national healthcare system. Lithuania and Poland, both at 51%, indicate a strongly critical perception, as does Chile at 48%. Greece and Hungary, each at 44%, indicate severe dissatisfaction, likely related to economic and structural problems in the healthcare system. Finally, Colombia closes the ranking with a concerning 41%, highlighting deep issues in the healthcare system

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that require urgent interventions to improve quality and access to care. These data suggest a vast disparity among countries in terms of satisfaction with the healthcare system, influenced by economic, political, and structural factors that vary greatly from one nation to another. The perception of healthcare quality is therefore a complex indicator that reflects not only the effectiveness of health policies but also the socio-economic and cultural context of each country.

Satisfaction with the Healthcare System in OECD Countries between 2017 and 2022. Analyzing the data on satisfaction with the healthcare system between 2017 and 2022 reveals a varied and complex picture of public perceptions in different countries. Generally, there is a widespread trend of decreasing satisfaction, although there are some significant exceptions that deserve attention. In Australia, satisfaction dropped by 5 percentage points, from 76% to 71%, a decrease of 6.58%. A similar decline is observed in Austria, where satisfaction decreased by 11 percentage points, from 92% to 81%, with a percentage change of 11.96%. In Belgium, the decrease is less marked, with a loss of 3 percentage points, from 93% to 90%, a change of 3.23%. Canada shows one of the largest decreases, with a loss of 13 percentage points, from 69% to 56%, a change of 18.84%. This indicates a significant deterioration in the perception of the healthcare system. Similarly, Colombia recorded a drop of 13 percentage points, from 54% to 41%, with a change of 24.07%, representing one of the worst performances among the analyzed countries. Costa Rica and Denmark registered more contained decreases, of 4 and 3 percentage points respectively, while in France, satisfaction dropped by 5 percentage points, from 79% to 74%, a change of 6.33%. Germany saw a decline of 8 percentage points, from 87% to 79%, a change of 9.20%. In Greece, satisfaction decreased by 8 percentage points, from 52% to 44%, with a change of 15.38%, while in Hungary the decline was 10 percentage points, from 54% to 44%, a change of 18.52%. Ireland and Poland remained stable, with satisfaction unchanged at 68% and 51%, respectively. In contrast, Israel saw an increase of 7 percentage points, from 68% to 75%, a change of 10.29%, and Italy registered an increase of 6 percentage points, from 56% to 62%, a change of 10.71%. South Korea and Latvia also saw significant increases, by 11 percentage points each (from 63% to 74%, a change of 17.46%, and from 49% to 60%, a change of 22.45%, respectively). Lithuania recorded a notable increase of 17 percentage points, from 34% to 51%, with a change of 50%. This data is particularly significant considering the low starting point. In Luxembourg, satisfaction decreased by 5 percentage points, from 90% to 85%, a change of 5.56%. In Mexico and the Slovak Republic, satisfaction increased by 2 percentage points each, with percentage changes of 3.64% and 3.45%. Portugal also saw an increase of 6 percentage points, from 57% to 63%, a change of 10.53%. Conversely, Slovenia registered a decrease of 10 percentage points, from 78% to 68%, with a change of 12.82%, while Spain saw a drop of 6 percentage points, from 73% to 67%, with a change of 8.22%. In Sweden, satisfaction decreased by 4 percentage points, from 78% to 74%, with a change of 5.13%. Switzerland is a notable exception, maintaining an unchanged satisfaction rate of 92%, demonstrating stability that many other countries have not managed to maintain. Turkey saw an increase of 4 percentage points, from 54% to 58%, with a change of 7.41%. The United Kingdom registered one of the largest decreases, with a loss of 13 percentage points, from 84% to 71%, a change of 15.48%, while in the United States, satisfaction decreased by 3 percentage points, from 78% to 75%, with a change of 3.85%. Analyzing these data reveals various trends and dynamics. Countries with the most significant declines, such as Canada, Colombia, New Zealand, and the United Kingdom, may have faced structural challenges or specific events that negatively impacted public perception. Conversely, countries like Estonia, Lithuania, and the Czech Republic, which saw significant increases, may have implemented reforms or improvements in the healthcare system that led to increased satisfaction. In conclusion, the data on satisfaction with the healthcare

system between 2017 and 2022 shows a heterogeneous landscape, with many nations experiencing a decrease in satisfaction, while others have seen improvements. These variations may reflect a combination of economic, political, and social factors that influence public perception of national healthcare systems.

Clustering with K-Means Algorithm Optimized with the Silhouette Coefficient. The clustering with the K-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient highlights the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 0: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Costa Rica, Czechia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Israel, Japan, Korea, Latvia, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United States. This cluster primarily includes countries that, both in 2017 and 2022, showed a relatively high level of satisfaction with their healthcare system. Many of these countries are known for having well-developed and well-funded healthcare systems. Many of these countries show some stability in their satisfaction levels, with small variations between 2017 and 2022. This suggests that citizens have positive and consistent perceptions of their healthcare systems. This cluster includes countries from various regions of the world, including Europe, Asia, Oceania, and the Americas, indicating that high levels of satisfaction can be achieved in various geographic and cultural contexts.
- Cluster 1: Canada, Chile, Colombia, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Mexico, New Zealand, Turkey, United Kingdom. This cluster comprises countries with levels of satisfaction that are generally lower or more variable compared to Cluster 0. Many of these countries have seen significant changes in the perception of their healthcare system between 2017 and 2022. The countries in this cluster may face various challenges in their healthcare systems, such as insufficient funding, inefficiencies in healthcare management, or socioeconomic pressures that affect the quality of healthcare services. Even though it includes countries with strong economies like Canada and the United Kingdom, this cluster also includes emerging economies like Mexico and Colombia. This suggests that healthcare challenges can exist in various economic contexts.

The presence of countries with high and low satisfaction levels in both clusters indicates the diversity in global healthcare systems. Factors such as healthcare policies, government investments, accessibility, and quality of healthcare services can significantly influence public perception. The clustering results can be useful for healthcare policymakers to identify best practices and areas for improvement. Countries in Cluster 1 could benefit from analyzing the strategies and structures implemented in countries in Cluster 0. In summary, the clustering highlights the differences in satisfaction levels with the healthcare system among countries, providing useful insights for improving healthcare policies and the efficiency of healthcare services globally.

Economic Policies to Improve Healthcare System Satisfaction. Economic policies aimed at improving satisfaction with the healthcare system in OECD countries must address a range of complex and interconnected challenges. First and foremost, it is essential to ensure adequate and sustainable funding for the healthcare system. This can be achieved through increased financial resources allocated to healthcare, either by raising specific taxes or by redistributing existing resources. Additionally, efficiency in resource allocation is crucial: investing in advanced healthcare

technologies, continuous training for medical staff, and infrastructure improvements can reduce long-term costs and improve the quality of services offered. Another important policy concerns universal access to healthcare services. Implementing universal health insurance systems can ensure that all citizens, regardless of income, have access to necessary care. This not only improves the overall health of the population but also increases satisfaction with the healthcare system. Furthermore, eliminating geographical barriers by expanding healthcare infrastructure in rural and remote areas is essential to ensure equitable access to services. Public health prevention policies play a critical role in improving satisfaction with the healthcare system. Investing in prevention programs, such as vaccination campaigns, screening programs, and promoting healthy lifestyles, can reduce the incidence of chronic diseases and improve quality of life. This preventive approach not only reduces pressure on the healthcare system but also increases positive perceptions among the population. The digitalization of the healthcare system represents another key area of intervention. The adoption of electronic health records, telemedicine, and other digital technologies can improve the efficiency, transparency, and accessibility of healthcare services. Telemedicine, in particular, has proven to be a powerful tool during the COVID-19 pandemic, allowing patients to access care without physically visiting clinics. This innovation not only improves accessibility but also patient satisfaction due to the greater convenience and speed of consultations. Improving working conditions for healthcare personnel is essential to ensure high-quality service and user satisfaction. Policies that provide adequate salaries, continuous training, career advancement opportunities, and a safe and supportive work environment can reduce burnout and increase the motivation of medical staff. Satisfied and motivated healthcare personnel are more likely to provide high-quality care, thus improving patient perception and satisfaction. Transparency and accountability in the healthcare system are fundamental to building trust among citizens. Implementing mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating healthcare performance, making results and evaluations public, can increase public trust in the system. Additionally, citizen participation in the decision-making process, through public consultations and the involvement of patient representatives, can make the healthcare system more responsive to the population's needs. Another crucial aspect is the integration of healthcare services with other social services. Many health determinants, such as education, employment, and the environment, are closely linked to the overall well-being of the population. Policies promoting integration between healthcare and social services can more effectively address the root causes of health inequalities. For example, programs combining healthcare with housing support for the homeless or mental health services integrated with employment support can significantly improve health outcomes and user satisfaction. Equity policies are crucial for improving satisfaction with the healthcare system. Ensuring that all individuals, regardless of their socio-economic background, ethnicity, gender, or place of residence, have access to high-quality healthcare is fundamental. This can be achieved through targeted policies to reduce inequalities, such as additional funding for disadvantaged areas, awareness and support programs for marginalized communities, and strategies to address the social determinants of health. Reforms in the pharmaceutical sector are equally important. Ensuring access to essential medicines at affordable prices, promoting competition, and regulating drug prices can reduce costs for patients and improve treatment adherence. Additionally, investing in the research and development of new drugs and innovative therapies can improve health outcomes and increase trust in the healthcare system. Finally, health education is a key component for improving satisfaction with the healthcare system. Informing and educating the population about available services, health rights, and how to navigate the healthcare system can reduce anxiety and confusion, increasing overall satisfaction. Awareness campaigns and educational programs in schools and communities can promote a culture of health and well-being, encouraging healthy behaviors and appropriate use of healthcare services.

Conclusions. Satisfaction with the healthcare system decreased between 2017 and 2022 by an average of -2.03% for the considered OECD countries. The countries where satisfaction with the healthcare system grew the most are Estonia with +65.00%, Lithuania with +50.00%, and Latvia with +22.45%. The countries where satisfaction with the healthcare system decreased the most are Canada with -18.84%, New Zealand with -20.99%, and Colombia with -24.07%.

Declarations

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Appendix

Clusterizzazione Della Soddisfazione Sanitaria Ottimizzata (K=2)

